

Equilibrium Studies of the Interaction of Vanadyl Ion with Tartaric and Malic Acids

K. Lal* and R. P. Agarwal

A quantitative study of the interaction of vanadyl (IV) ion with tartaric and malic acids has been carried out by the potentiometric titrations of vanadyl ion with KOH in the presence of varying concentrations of the ligands. Formation of 1:1 vanadyl tartrate and malate complexes has been indicated and the equilibrium constants of the reactions have been determined in a 0.1M KCl medium. On the basis of a mathematical analysis of the potentiometric data, probable reaction mechanisms have been suggested.

Although tartrate and malate complexes of vanadyl (IV) ion have been reported^{1,5} earlier in literature, systematic potentiometric study of the systems does not appear to have been done by the earlier workers. The present investigation was, therefore, undertaken to carry out a quantitative study of the equilibria involved in the interaction of vanadyl (IV) ion with tartaric and malic acids. In order to detect polymerization of the complexes, equilibrium constants were determined in a four-fold concentration range of the metal chelates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadyl sulphate solution was standardized by titrating with sodium hydroxide in the presence of an excess of disodium salt of EDTA according to the method of Schwarzenbach⁶. Strength of the solution was also checked⁷ by titrating the vanadyl sulphate solution with a standard solution of potassium permanganate using phosphoric acid as a catalyst and ferroin as an indicator. In order to prevent oxidation of the vanadyl sulphate solution known amount of a standard solution of HCl was added. This solution was then kept unchanged⁸ for two weeks at room temperature.

Tartaric and malic acids were of (B.D.H., Analar) reagents. Solutions of these acids were standardized by potentiometric titrations with a standard caustic potash solution (0.1N). Standardization of the caustic potash solution was effected by titrating against a standard potassium hydrogen phthalate.

A Cambridge pH-meter, standardized against a 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate, was used to determine the hydrogen ion concentration of the reaction

*Chemistry Department, M. M. College, Modinagar, (U. P.)

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mixtures. The experimental method consisted of the potentiometric titrations of tartaric and malic acids in the absence and in the presence of vanadyl sulphate. Known volumes of the standard solution of vanadyl sulphate and the chelating agent were pipetted into a titration cell and diluted to the desired volume. The ionic strength was maintained relatively constant by using a medium containing 0.1M potassium chloride and low concentrations of the ligand and the metal ion. These reaction mixtures were then titrated with the KOH solution (0.1N) and the hydrogen ion concentrations were determined by a number of successive readings after each addition of small increments of the standard alkali solution (0.1N). All the pH values of the solutions were measured at a constant temperature of $30^{\circ}\pm 1^{\circ}$ and the titrations were repeated twice to ensure the reproducibility of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Curves 0 and 0¹ (Figs. 1 and 2) for the potentiometric titration of tartaric and malic acids respectively with KOH exhibit a sharp inflexion at two moles of alkali per mole of the acid indicating that only the carboxylic protons of the ligands dissociate in acid solution and the alcoholic (OH) hydrogen atoms remain unaffected under the experimental conditions. A single inflexion also indicates that the successive dissociation steps of the carboxylic protons of the organic acids overlap. The dissociation constants of these acids were determined in a 0.1M KCl medium, a condition used in the present investigation, by the method reported by Speakman. These values are presented in table I.

TABLE I

Equilibrium Constants of the Chelates (Temp., 30°C; μ , 0.1 (KCl))

Ligand—Tartaric acid (Acid dissociation constants $-\log K_{a1} = 2.90\pm 0.03$, $-\log K_{a2} = 3.99\pm 0.02$)

$T_A = TM$	$-\log K$	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$
$5 \times 10^{-3}M$	5.56 ± 0.01	1.33 ± 0.02	6.57 ± 0.02
$2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$	5.57 ± 0.02	1.32 ± 0.02	6.54 ± 0.03
$1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$	5.55 ± 0.22	1.34 ± 0.01	6.59 ± 0.01

Ligand—Malic acid (Acid dissociation constants $-\log K_{a1} = 3.29\pm 0.02$, $-\log K_{a2} = 4.97\pm 0.02$)

$T_A = TM$	$-\log K$	$-\log K'$	$-\log K''$
$5 \times 10^{-3}M$	3.34 ± 0.01	7.51 ± 0.04	4.17 ± 0.03
$2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$	3.32 ± 0.02	7.58 ± 0.03	4.26 ± 0.02
$1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$	3.34 ± 0.01	7.57 ± 0.03	4.23 ± 0.04

Curves, 1, 2 and 3 (Fig. 1) represent a family of the pH titration curves of the 1 : 1 mixtures of vanadyl sulphate and tartaric acid of concentrations 5×10^{-3} , 2.5×10^{-3} and $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ respectively with KOH. These curves exhibit sharp inflexions at 'm' values of 3 and 4, where 'm' represents moles of base added per mole of the metal ion. Occurrence of the first inflexion point at $m=3$ indicates that either one of the hydroxy hydrogen atoms of the ligand dissociates as a result of chelation or that one water molecule of hydration of the vanadyl ion undergoes dissociation to give a hydroxy complex. If H_4A

represents a tartaric acid molecule, formulae of the above two alternative chelate species may be represented as :

The possibility of the formation of B may be considered less likely in view of the fact that the unchelated vanadyl ion itself does not undergo hydrolysis below *pH* 3.5 as may be seen from the values of the hydrolysis constants reported by Rossotti and Rossotti⁹. The reaction may thus be represented as :

If K be the equilibrium constant for the above reaction, we have

$$K = \frac{[\text{VOHA}] [\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{VO}^{2+}] [\text{H}_4\text{A}]} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

or K', the equilibrium quotient of the reaction,

may be expressed as :

$$K' = \frac{[\text{VOHA}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{VO}^{2+}] [\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and the acid-dissociation constants of tartaric acid may be defined by the equations :

$$K_{a1} = \frac{[\text{H}_3\text{A}^-] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}_4\text{A}]} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

and

$$K_{a2} = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2-}] [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{H}_3\text{A}^-]} \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

Although the exact behaviour of vanadyl ions towards hydrolysis is uncertain, however, assuming the values of $K_{h1}=10^{-6}$ and $K_{h2}=10^{-6.88}$, reported by Rossotti and Rossotti⁹, for the equilibria $\text{VO}^{2+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons \text{VO}(\text{OH})^{+} + \text{H}^+$ and $2\text{VO}^{2+} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightleftharpoons (\text{VO}(\text{OH})_2)^{2+} + 2\text{H}^+$ respectively it may be shown that the amount of the hydrolyzed species of the vanadyl ion present in solution is negligible as compared to the other species present in the equilibrium mixture. Consideration of these hydrolyzed vanadyl species was, therefore, not considered necessary in writing the material balance equations given below.

If T_M represents the total concentration of all the metal species and T_A that of the various ligand species and if T_{OH} be the amount of alkali added to the reaction mixture during titration, we have

$$T_M = [\text{VO}^{2+}] + [\text{VOHA}] \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$T_{\text{OH}} + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{H}_3\text{A}^-] + 2[\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2-}] + 3[\text{VOHA}] \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

$$T_A = [\text{H}_4\text{A}] + [\text{H}_3\text{A}^-] + [\text{H}_2\text{A}^{2-}] + [\text{VOHA}] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

In the pH range studies the concentrations of HA^{3-} , A^{4-} and OH^- were negligible as compared to the other species present. Combination of the equations 3, 4, 6 and 7 gives :

$$[\text{H}_4\text{A}] = \frac{3T_A - T_{\text{OH}} - [\text{H}^+]}{3 + \frac{2K_{a1}}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2}}{[\text{H}^+]^2}} \quad \dots (8)$$

Concentration of the chelate species is given by

$$[\text{VOHA}^-] = T_A - [\text{H}_4\text{A}] \left(1 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{K_{a1} K_{a2}}{[\text{H}^+]^2} \right) \quad \dots (9)$$

Concentration of free vanadyl ion $[\text{VO}^{2+}]$ may then be calculated from equation 5. The values of the equilibrium constants, K and K' , may thus be determined. The mean values of these constants calculated at various points of the lower buffer region (m , 0.30—1.40) of the titration curves 1, 2 and 3 (Fig. 1) are listed in table I.

From the values of the equilibrium constants, determined in a four-fold concentration range of the metal chelate, it is evident that the chelate is present in solution mainly as a monomer under the experimental conditions. A slight shift of the low buffer regions of the curves 1, 2 and 3 (Fig. 1) with a variation in the concentration of the metal chelate may be accounted for entirely on the basis of variation of the degree of dissociation of the acid forms as a function of concentration and no condensation of the metal chelate thus seems to occur.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of vanadyl tartrate chelate systems with KOH (0.1N). Curve O, $5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in tartaric acid; curve 1, $5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ and $5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in tartaric acid; curve 2, $2.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ and $2.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in tartaric acid; curve 3, $1.25 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ and $1.25 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in tartaric acid; curve 4, $4.5 \times 10^{-3}\text{M}$ in $\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ and $1.0 \times 10^{-2}\text{M}$ in tartaric acid. In the lower buffer regions portion of the curves for the neutralization of HCl present in $\text{VO}(\text{IV})$ sol. has been eliminated.

Occurrence of the upper buffer region in the pH range 6-7 and an inflexion point at $m=4$ indicates that either the hydrogen of the second hydroxy group of the ligand dissociates and the tartrate ion acts as a quadridentate ligand as reported by Jorgensen³ or a water molecule of the vanadyl ion undergoes dissociation in which case the tartrate ion appears to behave as a tridentate ligand as shown by Feldman and Coworkers¹⁰ in the uranyl-tartrate chelates. These possible chelate species may be formulated as :

From the potentiometric data alone it seems to be difficult to distinguish between the above two possibilities. However, the formation of C, reported by Jorgensen is supported by Morpurgo and Selbin¹¹.

If we consider the structure C of the chelate, the acid dissociation of the chelate A may be represented as :

The equilibrium constant K'' may be expressed as :

$$K'' = \frac{[\text{VOA}^{2-}][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{VOHA}]} \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Mean values of $-\log K''$ determined at various points of the upper buffer regions of curves 1,2 and 3 (Fig. 1) are shown in the table I. Concentration independence of these values indicated that the chelate does not polymerize under the experimental conditions. Beyond the cross-over point at $m=4$, displacement of the curves to higher pH regions with an increase in the concentration of the metal chelate may be accounted for on the basis of the free hydroxide ion present, since different quantities of the KOH solution were required to produce the same value of 'm'.

The potentiometric titration curve 4 (Fig. 1) obtained for a solution containing a 1 : 2 molar ratio of vanadyl sulphate to tartaric acid corresponds to that which would be predicted for a mixture of the 1 : 1 chelate and the free ligand.

Vanadyl Malate Chelate : Like the vanadyl tartrate chelate system, in this case also the potentiometric titration curves of the 1 : 1 mixtures of the vanadyl sulphate and malic acid, in a four-fold concentration range (Curves 1-3, fig. 2). exhibited sharp inflexions at three and four moles of alkali per mole of the metal ion. If H_3A represents malic acid having two strongly acidic carboxylic protons and one weakly acidic hydroxy hydrogen, an inflexion point at $m=3$ indicates the formation of the chelate VOA^- and the same argument appears to hold for its formation as given in the case of vanadyl tartrate chelate system.

In this system, however, calculation of the equilibrium constant on the basis of the reaction :

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11. L. Morpurgo and J. Selbin, Unpublished work; *Chem. Reviews*, 1965, **65**, 153.

could not give a constant value. A gradual increase in the value of equilibrium constant was observed with an increase in the pH of the reaction mixture. At initial stages of the titration, attempts were, therefore, made to analyse the experimental data on the basis of the reaction :

and the method for the determination of equilibrium constant is outlined below :

The equilibrium constant K of the above reaction may be expressed as :

$$K = \frac{[VOHA] [H^+]^2}{[H_3A] [VO^{2+}]} \quad (11)$$

or k , the formation constant of the chelate may be given by

$$K = \frac{[VOHA]}{[VO^{2+}] [HA^{2-}]} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

other pertinent equations are :

$$T_M = [VO^{2+}] + [VOHA] \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = [H_2A^-] + 2[HA^{2-}] + 2[VOHA] \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

$$T_A = [H_3A] + [H_2A^-] + [HA^{2-}] + [VOHA] \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

As indicated in the vanadyl tartrate system, in this case also in the lower buffer region, the concentrations of the species $VO(OH)^+$, $(VO(OH)_2)^{2+}$, A^{3-} and OH^- were negligible as compared to the other species present in the reaction mixture.

From equations, given above, it may be shown that :

$$[H_3A] = \frac{2T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+]}{2 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[H^+]}} \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

and

$$[VOHA] = T_A - [H_3A] \left(1 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[H^+]} + \frac{K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2}}{[H^+]^2} \right) \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

Knowing the values of the dissociation constants, K_{a1} and K_{a2} of malic acid (Table I), concentrations of the other species present in solution may then be calculated from equations 13-15. Calculation of K gave essentially constant values in the range $m=0$ to $m=1.1$, above which a gradual fall in the values of $-\log K$ was observed. Mean values of the equilibrium constants calculated from the titration data of curves 1-3 (Fig. 2) are presented in table I.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of vanadyl malate chelate systems with $\text{KOH}(0.1N)$. Curve 0, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in malic acid; curve 1, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in VO(IV) and $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in malic acid; curve 2, $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in VO(IV) and $2.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in malic acid; curve 3, $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ in VO(IV) and $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ in malic acid; curve 4, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ in VO(IV) and $1.0 \times 10^{-2}M$ in malic acid. In the lower buffer region portion of the curve for the neutralization of HCl present in VO(IV) soln. has been eliminated.

It is evident that the values of $-\log K$ are almost independent of the concentration of the metal chelate indicating that the complex does not polymerize under the experimental conditions.

A gradual fall in the values of $-\log K$ above 'm' values of about 1.1 indicated that the protonated complex, VOHA , undergoes acid dissociation giving the chelate VOA^- . The reaction may be represented as :

The equilibrium constant, K' for the reaction may be expressed as :

$$K' = \frac{[\text{VOA}^-][\text{H}^+]}{[\text{VOHA}]} \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

or the formation of VOA^- may also be represented by the reaction :

The equilibrium constant, K'' , for the reaction may be given by :

$$K'' = \frac{[\text{VOA}^-][\text{H}^+]^3}{[\text{VO}^{2+}][\text{H}_3\text{A}]} \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

A single inflexion point at $m=3$ indicated that there is overlapping between the successive steps of the formation of the chelate species VOHA and VOA^- .

From the usual material balance we have,

$$T_M = [VO^{2+}] + [VOHA] + [VOA] \quad \dots (20)$$

$$T_{OH} + [H^+] = [H_2A^-] + 2[HA^{2-}] + 2[VOHA] + 3[VOA] \quad \dots (21)$$

$$T_A = [H_3A] + [H_2A^-] + [HA^{2-}] + [VOHA] + [VOA] \quad \dots (22)$$

Combination of equations 11 and 20-22 gives :

$$[VO^{2+}] = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 + 4ac}}{2a} \quad \dots (23)$$

where

$$a = \frac{K}{[H^+]^2 X}, \quad b = \frac{Y}{X}, \quad c = 3T_A - T_{OH} - [H^+] \text{ and}$$

$$X = 1 + \frac{K_{a1}}{[H^+]} + \frac{K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2}}{[H^+]^2}, \quad Y = 3 + \frac{2K_{a1}}{[H^+]} + \frac{K_{a1} \cdot K_{a2}}{[H^+]^2}$$

After computation of the equilibrium concentration of the free vanadyl ions, concentrations of the other species present in solution could then be calculated from equations 20-22. The values of K' and K'' could thus be found out. Mean values of these constants determined from the titration data of curves 1-3 (Fig. 2) are given in table I.

In this case also, concentration independence of the constants, indicated that the chelate VOA does not condense to give complex species of higher molecular weight. A slight spread of the low buffer regions seen in the curves 1-3 (Fig. 1), thus, can be entirely accounted for on the basis of the degree of dissociation of the acid forms as a function of concentration.

Hydrolysis of Vanadyl Malate Chelate : Appearance of the buffer region between $m=3$ and $m=4$ in the curves 1-3 (Fig. 2) with an inflexion at $m=4$ indicated that water molecule of the aquo chelate, $VOA(H_2O)^-$ undergoes dissociation giving a hydroxo complex. The equilibrium constant, K_H , of the reaction :

may be expressed as :

$$K_H = \frac{[VO(OH)A] [H^+]}{[VOA]} \quad \dots (24)$$

The mean values of $-\log K_H$, calculated from the titration data of the curves 1,2 and 3 (Fig. 2) were found to be 6.56 ± 0.02 , 6.54 ± 0.02 and 6.54 ± 0.03 respectively indicating that the hydroxo complex also does not polymerize in the solution.

As indicated in the vanadyl tartrate system, in this case also curve 4 (Fig. 2) for the potentiometric titration of vanadyl sulphate with KOH in presence of two moles of malic acid, may be explained on the basis of the formation of 1 : 1 chelate and the neutralization of the excess of malic acid (one mole) present in the reaction mixture.

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CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
UNIVERSITY OF ROORKEE,
ROORKEE, INDIA.

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